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National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina
Zmaja od Bosne 3, 71 000 Sarajevo,
Bosna i Hercegovina/Bosnia and Herzegovina
Telefon/Phone +387 (0)33 262 710
e-mail: kontakt@zemaljskimuzej.ba
<http://www.zemaljskimuzej.ba>

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Proučavanje transhumantnog stočarstva u istočnoj Hercegovini kroz integrativnu arheologiju

Examining Transhumant Pastoralism in Eastern Herzegovina through an Integrative Archaeology

SAŠA ČAVAL,¹ AGNI PRIJATELJ,² MARKO ZUPAN,³ ROK TURNIŠKI,⁴ LUKA ŠKERJANEC,⁵ LUCIJA GRAHEK,⁶ MONIKA MILOSAVLJEVIĆ,⁷ ŽIGA KOKALJ⁸

¹ Institut za antropološke i prostorne studije, Istraživački centar Slovenske akademije nauka i umjetnosti, Novi trg 2, Ljubljana 1000, Slovenija; Univerzitet Primorska, Odsjek za arheologiju i baštinu, Titov trg 1, Kopar 6000, Slovenija: scaval@zrc-sazu.si ^{2, 3,}

⁴ Centar za tlo i okoliš, Biotehnički fakultet, Univerzitet u Ljubljani, Jamnikarjeva ulica 101, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenija: agni.prijatelj@bf.uni-lj.si, marko.zupan@bf.uni-lj.si, rok.turniski@bf.uni-lj.si

^{5, 6, 8} Institut za antropološke i prostorne studije, Istraživački centar Slovenske akademije nauka i umjetnosti, Novi trg 2, Ljubljana 1000, Slovenija: luka.skerjanec@zrc-sazu.si, lucija.grahek@zrc-sazu.si ziga.kokalj@zrc-sazu.si

⁷ Odsjek za arheologiju, Filozofski fakultet, Univerzitet u Beogradu, Čika Ljubina 18–20, Beograd, Srbija: momilosa@f.bg.ac.rs

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Iako se planinski krajolik zapadnog Balkana danas samo povremeno koristi za ispašu, on je sastavni dio pastoralnih krajolika još od prahistorije. Izazov je, međutim, kako pomoću arheologije prepoznati prisutnost transhumantnog stočarstva u takvim područjima. Ovaj članak je integrativno arheološko transdisciplinarno istraživanje historijske planinske pastirske stanice – katuna – na planinama Crvanj i Morine iznad Nevesinja u Hercegovini. Grupa stručnjaka za daljinsko istraživanje i prostor, arheologa prethistoričara i medijevista, gearheologa i pedologa, od kojih svaki donosi jedinstvenu perspektivu, usredotočila se na dva ljetna pastoralna kampa, lokalno nazvana katuni Busovača i Tarasovača, kako bi razumjeli izuzetnu i dugotrajnu prisutnost ljudi na ovom gorju.

Ključne riječi: transhumanca, historijska arheologija, prahistorija, Dinarske Alpe, Hercegovina, daljinska detekcija, arheologija objekata, gearheologija, nauka o tlu, stećci

Although the mountainous countryside of the Western Balkans is today only used occasionally for grazing, it has formed an integral part of pastoral landscapes since prehistoric times. The challenge, however, is how to recognise the presence of transhumance in such areas through archaeology. This article presents the integrative archaeological transdisciplinary research of a historical mountain pastoral station – a *katun* – on the Crvanj and Morine mountains above Nevesinje in Herzegovina. A group of remote sensing and spatial experts, prehistoric and medieval archaeologists, gearchaeologists and soil scientists, each bringing their own unique perspective to the study, focused on two summer pastoral camps, locally named the Busovača and Tarasovača katuns, to understand the remarkable long-established occupation of these highlands.

Keywords: transhumance, historical archaeology, prehistory, Dinaric Alps, Herzegovina, remote sensing, standing archaeology, gearchaeology, soil science, stećci

UVOD

Istraživanje prikazano u ovom radu proizlazi iz transdisciplinarnog istraživanja srednjovjekovnih spomenika stećaka. Ove grobne oznake podigle su između dvanaestog i šesnaestog vijeka naše ere zajednice koje su živjele na teritorijama današnje Hrvatske, Crne Gore, Srbije, a posebno Bosne i Hercegovine. Stećci ostaju razbacani *in situ* po krajolicima i služe svojoj izvornoj namjeni, podsjećajući nas na imanentnost vremena. Oni su jedan od najbolje očuvanih, ali najmanje proučenih primjera evropske srednjovjekovne kulturne baštine. Više od 72.000 stećaka koji su još uvijek sačuvani *in situ*, preko 60.000 se nalazi u Bosni i Hercegovini. Njihova disperzirana distribucija i brojnost bili su prepreka njihovom proučavanju, posebno iz arheološke perspektive.¹

Prisustvo stećaka nije ograničeno na neko određeno mjesto. Nalaze se uz puteve ili dalje od njih, u nizinama, dolinama, na vrhovima brežuljaka, uz vodu, ali i u poljima, na livadama, u šumama, uz crkve, u selima, ali i daleko od naselja. Oni se, što je posebno zanimljivo, mogu pronaći i na visokim planinskim lancima, na 1300 metara nadmorske visine, pa i više. Postojanje stećaka na takvim mjestima može se pripisati ekonomiji kasnog Srednjeg vijeka, konkretno transhumanci. S obzirom na višestruka tumačenja pastoralizma i transhumance,² autori ovog članka žele naglasiti da selidbu vide kao sezonsko kretanje stoke, u ovom slučaju prvenstveno ovaca, između označenih ljetnih planinskih i zimskih nizinskih pašnjaka, bilo pod nadzorom pastira ili svojih vlasnika.

Ekonomija Mediterana, a posebno Balkana, historijski je bila usko povezana s transhumantnim stočarstvom, a dokazi o prahistorijskim i srednjovjekovnim stočarskim praksama često se preklapaju.³ Arheološki dokazi iz istočne i srednje Evrope upućuju na minimalno korištenje planinskih područja tokom neolita (6500–3300 p.n.e. n. e.) i intenziviranje tokom eneolita i bronzanog doba (3300–1000 p.n.e. n. e.).⁴ Širenje u planinska područja na kraju neolita uključivalo je široko usvajanje transhumantnog stočarstva kao dijela cjelokupne strategije uzgoja domaćih životinja.⁵ Kako su periodična vertikalna kretanja povezana s ekstremnim ekološkim uslovima, s velikom sezonskom varijabilnošću klime,⁶ transhumanca je vrlo vjerovatno bila zastupljena u prahistorijskoj, postneolitskoj Hercegovini. Naše arheološko istraživanje prahistorijskih tumulusa, ograđenih prostora i sličnih krajolika u ovoj mikroregiji moglo bi poslužiti kao primjer za provjeru općih ideja o transhumanci u prahistoriji.

Krško okruženje Hercegovine je u srednjem vijeku ponovo postalo blisko povezano sa transhumancom i duboko

INTRODUCTION

The investigation presented here stems from transdisciplinary research of medieval *stećak* (pl. *stećci*) monuments. These burial markers were erected between the 12th and 16th centuries CE by the communities that lived on the territories of modern Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia, and particularly Bosnia and Herzegovina. The *stećci* remain scattered *in situ* across landscapes, serving their original purpose and reminding us of the immanence of time. They are one of the best-preserved yet least-studied examples of European medieval cultural heritage. From more than 72,000 *stećci* still preserved *in situ*, over 60,000 can be found in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Their dispersed distribution and large numbers have in many ways acted as a hindrance to their scholarship, especially from an archaeological perspective.¹

The presence of *stećci* is not limited to any specific location or landscape. They can be found beside roads or away from them, in lowland plains, in valleys, and on hilltops, by water or in fields, meadows, or forests, adjacent to churches, in villages, or far away from settled areas. Intriguingly, they can also be found on high mountain ranges, at elevations of 1300 metres above sea level (ASL) and even higher. The existence of *stećci* in such places can be attributed to the economy of the Late Medieval period, specifically to transhumance. Given the multiple interpretations of pastoralism and transhumance,² the authors of this article wish to emphasise that they see transhumance as the seasonal movement of livestock, in this case primarily sheep, between designated summer mountain and winter lowland pastures, either under the care of herders or in the company of their owners.

The economy of the Mediterranean, and the Balkans in particular, has historically been closely connected to transhumant pastoralism, with evidence of prehistoric and medieval pastoral practices frequently overlapping.³ Archaeological evidence from Eastern and Central Europe suggests a minimal use of highland areas during the Neolithic period (6500–3300 BCE) and intensification during the Eneolithic and Bronze Age (3300–1000 BCE).⁴ The expansion into upland areas at the end of the Neolithic involved the widespread adoption of transhumant pastoralism as part of the overall strategy for managing domestic animals.⁵ As periodic vertical movements are related to extreme ecological conditions with high seasonal variability in climate,⁶ transhumance may be considered a highly probable phenomenon in prehistoric post-Neolithic Herzegovina. Our archaeological research of prehistoric burial mounds, enclosures and associated landscapes in this micro-region could serve as an example to test general ideas on transhumance in prehistory.

1 Bešlagić 1982; Lovrenović 2009; Bujak 2018.

2 Vojvodić 2021. i tu navedena literatura.

3 Bartosiewicz, Greenfield 1999; Mlekuž 2003; Barker 2005; Arnold, Greenfield 2006; Carrer 2015; Costello, Svensson 2018; Horvat 2019; Andrić *et al.* 2020; Caf *et al.* 2023; Mlekuž Vrhovnik, Fabec 2024.

4 Greenfield 2001.

5 Greenfield 1999.

6 Porčić 2008, 7–9, 22–23.

1 Bešlagić 1982; Lovrenović 2009; Bujak 2018.

2 Vojvodić 2021 and the literature presented there.

3 Bartosiewicz, Greenfield 1999; Mlekuž 2003; Barker 2005; Arnold, Greenfield 2006; Carrer 2015; Costello, Svensson 2018; Horvat 2019; Andrić *et al.* 2020; Caf *et al.* 2023; Mlekuž Vrhovnik, Fabec 2024.

4 Greenfield 2001.

5 Greenfield 1999.

6 Porčić 2008, 7–9, 22–23.

je vezano za katun.⁷ Iako se danas shvata kao historijska planinska pastirska stanica ili mjesto posebne arhitekture, vezano za životinjske (i ljudske) potrebe i zahtjeve, katun je u prošlosti bio složena društvena organizacija etničke/socijalne grupe Vlaha/vlaha. Vlasi su bili vezani za transhumanu, gdje su plemenski vezivali domaćinstva u katune. Vlast bi imenovala jednog katunara, obično muškarca, da djeluje kao njihov predstavnik. Iako se katunsko starješinstvo moglo dodijeliti ženi, to je bilo izuzetno rijetko. Značajno je da se u arhivskim zapisima spominje samo jedna: "katunarka Jelena", postavljena 1443. godine za starješinu katuna Vragović. Taj je sistem pomogao da se osigura društvena autonomija Vlaha/vlaha⁸ u feudalizmu.⁹

Prema etnografskim i historijskim izvorima, čini se da je sistem transhumantnih katuna slijedio obrazac poželjnih brdskih lokacija. Čini se da su izvori pitke vode uticali na odabir ljetnih pašnjaka. Male visoravni u podnožju planinskih vrhova, s naslagama glacialne morene¹⁰ i valovitim terenom, odabrane su kao područja sa dovoljno sunčeve svjetlosti i zavjetrine, što je omogućavalo udobno naseljavanje. Prema dostupnim izvorima, sagrađene su međe i kuće od kamene (pot)konstrukcije i lakših građevinskih materijala.¹¹

STUDIJA SLUČAJA

Busovača i Tarasovača, dva vitalno vezana katuna, smještene su na visokoj zaravni na oko 1400 metara nadmorske visine, gdje planina Crvanj prelazi u visoravan Morine (sl. 1). Područje je odabrano kao ključna tačka za naše istraživanje historijskih pastirskih zajednica zbog svoje geografske izoliranosti, prirodno zaštićenog pašnjaka s niskom vegetacijom i dva izvora vode, što ga sve čini idealnim za naseljavanje. Dolina je napuštena tokom prošlog vijeka i danas se do nje može doći samo pješice ili terenskim vozilom.

Tim stručnjaka za paleoekološke i prostorne studije, podatke i tehnologije, prahistoriju, srednjovjekovne studije i kulturnu baštinu do sada je proveo dvije etape sezonskog integrativnog istraživanja (septembar 2023. i 2024.). Na osnovu obima područja i detaljnog uvida u datu lokaciju ili ukup, usvojili smo višestruki pristup, efikasno prelazeći od makroposmatranja do mikroposmatranja arheološke karakteristike, tj. od krajolika lokacije do hemijskog sastava tla i mikrobiološke analize ljudskih i životinjskih kostiju. Ta nam višeslojnost dopušta da čitamo prošle krajolike ne kao

The karst environment of Herzegovina became again closely associated with transhumance during the medieval period, and was profoundly centred on the *katun*.⁷ Although today understood as a historical mountain pastoral station or location with distinct architecture tending to animal (and human) needs and requirements, the katun of the past was a complex social organisation attributed to the Vlach/vlach ethnic/social group. The Vlachs were associated with medieval transhumance, where kinship linked households into katuns. The ruling authority would appoint one *katunar*, typically a male, to act as their representative. Although the seniority of the katun could be assigned to a female, this was extremely rare. Notably, archival records mention only one: the "katunarka Jelena" was appointed as the head of the Vragović katun in 1443. This system helped secure the social autonomy of the Vlachs/vlachs⁸ within feudalism.⁹

Based on ethnographic and historical sources, the transhumant katun system seems to have followed a pattern of preferable upland locations. Sources of fresh drinking water appear to have influenced the choice of summer pastures. Small plateaus at the foot of mountain peaks, with glacial moraine deposits¹⁰ and undulating terrain, were chosen as areas where sufficient sunlight and slopes, protecting from the wind, allowed for comfortable settling. Based on the available resources, the erected enclosures and houses were made of a stone (sub)structure and lighter building materials.¹¹

THE CASE STUDY

Busovača and Tarasovača, two vitally concomitant katuns, are located in a high-altitude valley at approximately 1400 metres ASL, where Crvanj mountain merges into the Morine plateau (Fig. 1). The area was selected as the focal point for our study on historical pastoral communities due to its geographic isolation, naturally protected pastureland with low vegetation, and two water sources, all of which make it ideal for settlement. The valley has been abandoned during the past century, and can today only be reached on foot or by an off-road vehicle.

To date, the team of specialists in paleoenvironmental and spatial studies, data and technologies, prehistory, medieval studies and cultural heritage has conducted two seasons of systematic integrative research (September 2023 and 2024). Based on the extent of the area and detailed insights into a given location or burial, we adopted a multiscale approach, effectively zooming in from a macro- to

7 Kovačević 1963; Đurđev 1963, 144–145.

8 Od 14. vijeka nadalje, balkanski dokumentarni izvori sve više spominju vlaške zajednice, prvenstveno ih karakterizirajući kao stočare, koji se bave transhumancom – sezonskim kretanjem ljudi i životinja koje je bilo usko vezano uz uzgoj konja, goveda i ovaca. Iako su tipično nosili slavenska imena, naseljene zajednice u Hercegovini i lučkim gradovima, poput Raguse (Dubrovnik, moderna Hrvatska), često su ih doživljavale kao "druge". Ostaje nejasno jesu li oni tokom srednjeg vijeka činili zasebnu etničku ili samo određenu društvenu grupu.

9 Hrabak 1981, 183–185; Petrović 1986, 12; Luković 2015, 31–38; Isailović 2017, 25–35.

10 Morene, odnosno akumulacija ostataka, koje se javljaju u ledenjačkim regijama koje je prethodno nosio glečer / glečerski pokrov, sastoje se od stjenovitih terena čija veličina varira od pijeska i gline do gromada.

11 Trifunovski 1963, 30–31; Filipović 1963; Vojvodić 2021, 74.

7 Kovačević 1963, 121–139; Đurđev 1963, 144–145.

8 From the 14th century onward, Balkan documentary sources increasingly mention Vlach communities, primarily characterising them as livestock breeders, engaged in transhumance – a seasonal movement of people and animals that was closely tied to the breeding of horses, cattle, and sheep. Although they typically bore Slavic names, they were frequently perceived as "other" by settled communities in Hercegovina and port cities, such as Ragusa (Dubrovnik, modern Croatia). It remains unclear whether they constituted a distinct ethnic group or only a specific social group during the Middle Ages.

9 Hrabak 1981, 183–185; Petrović 1986, 12; Luković 2015, 31–38; Isailović 2017, 25–35.

10 Debris accumulation, occurring in glaciated regions previously transported along by the glacier/ice sheet, moraines consist of rocky terrains that range in size from sand and clay to boulders.

11 Trifunovski 1963, 30–31; Filipović 1963, 45; Vojvodić 2021, 74.

Sl. 1. Topografska karta nalazišta i planine Crvanj i visoravni Morine unutar šire regije (autor: L. Škerjanec).

Fig. 1. Topographic map of the sites and the Crvanj mountain and Morine plateau within the wider region (author: L. Škerjanec).

fosilizirane zapise o tome kako su ljudi koristili zemlju u prošlosti, već kao fragmente fluidnih medija kroz koje su oboje, ekonomija i društveni životi organizirani i praktikovani.¹²

Naše prvo izviđanje planine Crvanj i visoravni Morine bilo je u junu 2023. godine, kada smo bili u kratkoj posjeti kako bismo stekli preliminarni uvid u to područje. Zbog gusto obraslog terena s visokom travom i šikarom, nismo mogli razaznati nikakve sisteme gradnje, jedva neke pojedinačne ili druge popratne stočarske, poljoprivredne ili pomoćne objekte. Stoga smo se vratili za radne stolove i oslonili na savremene tehnologije. Kako bismo stekli uvid u nivo antropogenog uticaja na okoliš, naše kolege stručnjaci za daljinsku detekciju dostavili su nam prostorni prikaz područja. Informacije su bile detaljne i iznad svega korisne za naše buduće istraživanje.

S ovim informacijama krenuli smo u drugo istraživanje u septembru 2023. Cilj nam je bio istražiti područje i povezati prostorni izvještaj sa situacijom na terenu, locirati katune Busovača i Tarasovača,¹³ identificirati namjerno izgrađene

micro-observation of an archaeological feature, i.e. from a landscape to a site to a chemical composition of the soil and microbiological analyses of human and animal bones. This multiscalarity permits us to read the past landscapes not as fossilised records of how people utilised the land in the past, but as fragments of fluid media through which both, economy and social life were organised and practised.¹²

Our first reconnaissance of the Crvanj mountain and Morine plateau was in June 2023, when we paid a short visit to gain a preliminary insight into the area. Due to the densely overgrown terrain with high grasses and shrubbery, it was not possible to distinguish any systematic constructions, with individual structures and associated pastoral, agricultural or auxiliary buildings barely visible. We therefore returned to desk-based research and modern technologies. To understand the level of anthropogenic impact on the environment, our remote sensing specialist colleagues provided us with a spatial overview of the area. This information was detailed and, above all, instrumental to our future research.

Equipped with this knowledge, we embarked on our second survey in September 2023. We aimed to explore the

¹² Mlekuž Vrhovnik, Fabec 2024; Barret 1988, 9.

¹³ Klastere farmi Busovača i Tarasovača proizvodljno smo nazvali prema dvjema lokvama, identificiranim i imenovanim na (starim) kartama. Međutim, ljudi

¹² Mlekuž Vrhovnik, Fabec 2024; Barret 1988, 9.

objekte, njihovu namjenu, moguće izvore vode te potencijalna popratna groblja. Tada nam je hronološki okvir nalazišta bio od sekundarne važnosti. Prvo, primijetili smo da je vegetacije puno manje nego ljeti. Trave su bile niže, a grmlje je već izgubilo sve lišće. Nije bilo iznenađenje što smo naišli na brojne kamene strukture različitih veličina i oblika koje je izgradio čovjek.

U nastavku članka predstavljamo uredsko istraživanje, terenski rad i laboratorijsko istraživanje protekle dvije sezone.

DALJINSKA DETEKCIJA

Najbolja arhiva zračnih ili satelitskih snimaka za područje zapadnog Balkana, a posebno za područje bivše Jugoslavije, nalazi se u Vojnogeografskom institutu "General Stevan Bošković" u Beogradu u Srbiji. Zbog količine materijala koji se tamo čuva i administrativnih postupaka za ostvarenje pristupa, još uvijek smo u procesu prikupljanja relevantnih podataka, te ovdje oni nisu prikazani. Umjesto toga, za detaljan pregled planine Crvanj i visoravni Morine koristili smo tri međunarodna izvora snimaka daljinskog istraživanja: historijske arhive zračnih fotografija, američke špijunske satelitske programe iz doba Hladnog rata i savremene komercijalne satelitske snimke vrlo visoke rezolucije. Brojne su prednosti korištenja vojnih izviđačkih slika s kojih je skinuta oznaka tajnosti za arheološka istraživanja.¹⁴ U kombinaciji s fotografijama iz zraka, one nude jedinstvene mogućnosti za posmatranje promjenjivog krajolika pašnjaka u tom području.

Nacionalna zbirka zračnih fotografija (engl. *National Collection of Aerial Photography*, NCAP) dio je nezavisnog tijela Historijski okoliš Škotske (engl. *Historic Environment Scotland*) i čuva nekoliko međunarodnih arhiva koje sadrže milione historijskih zračnih slika iz cijele Evrope. Najrelevantnije zbirke za naše područje istraživanja su one Njemačkih zračnih snaga (GX),¹⁵ Zajedničkog obavještajnog centra za zračno izviđanje (engl. *Joint Air Reconnaissance Intelligence Centre*, JARIC),¹⁶ Sredozemnog savezničkog fotoizviđačkog krila (engl. *Mediterranean Allied Photo Reconnaissance Wing*, MAPRW),¹⁷ a posebno Centralne savezničke jedinice za tumačenje fotografija (engl. *Allied Central Interpretation Unit*, ACIU).¹⁸ Trenutno je izuzetno mali broj tih fotografija digitaliziran. Iako NCAP najvjerojatnije posjeduje najranije, relativno lako dostupne fotografije iz zraka velike pokrivenosti zapadne Hercegovine, nije se moglo pristupiti svim originalnim okvirima jer ponekad postoje samo skenirane kopije niske rezolucije. Naša potraga za fotografijama iz Drugog

area and correlate the spatial report with the on-the-ground situation, locate the Busovača and Tarasovača¹³ katuns, and identify intentionally built structures, their purposes, possible water sources, and potential accompanying burial grounds. At the time, the chronological framework of the site held secondary significance. First, we noticed the vegetation was far less dense than in the summer period. The grasses were shorter, and the shrubbery had already lost its foliage. Not surprisingly, we encountered numerous human-made stone structures of different sizes and shapes.

The following presents the desk-based, fieldwork and laboratory research of the past two seasons.

REMOTE SENSING

The most suitable archive of aerial or satellite imagery for the Western Balkans region, and especially for the territory of the former Yugoslavia, is housed at Vojnogeografski Institut General Stevan Bošković, in Belgrade, Serbia. Due to the amount of material curated there and administrative procedures pertaining to its access, we are still in the process of acquiring the relevant data; thus, they are not presented here. Instead, in order to achieve a detailed overview of the Crvanj mountain and Morine plateau, we used three international sources of remote sensing imagery: historical archives of aerial photographs, the Cold War-era United States spy satellite programmes, and modern, high-resolution commercial satellite imagery. The benefits of using declassified military reconnaissance images for archaeological research are numerous.¹⁴ Combined with aerial photography, they offer unique opportunities for observation of the changing pasture landscape of the area.

The National Collection of Aerial Photography (NCAP) is part of the Historic Environment Scotland's holdings, and includes several international archives containing millions of historical aerial images from across Europe. The most relevant collections for our study area are the German Air Force (GX),¹⁵ Joint Air Reconnaissance Intelligence Centre (JARIC),¹⁶ Mediterranean Allied Photo Reconnaissance Wing (MAPRW),¹⁷ and especially the Allied Central Interpretation Unit (ACIU).¹⁸ Presently, only a very small portion of these images have been digitised. Although the NCAP potentially holds the earliest, relatively easily accessible, large-coverage aerial photographs of western Herzegovina, not all the original frames could be retrieved, as sometimes only low-resolution scanned copies exist. Our search for relevant photographs dating to World War II has also not been successful

danas tu dolinu nazivaju Busovača, a ime Tarasovača je zaboravljeno. Ova promjena u korištenju imena mogla bi se pripisati promjenama u lokalnoj demografiji i kulturnim uticajima tokom vremena. Pored toga, historijski događaji ili administrativne odluke mogli su odigrati ulogu u postepenom uklanjanju imena Tarasovača (vidi Puljić 2010, Naumović, Dražeta 2023).

14 Npr. Hanson, Oltean 2013.

15 NCAP 2024b.

16 NCAP 2024c.

17 NCAP 2024d.

18 NCAP 2024a.

13 We arbitrarily named the farm clusters Busovača and Tarasovača after the two water ponds, identified and named on the (old) maps. However, people today call the valley Busovača, and the name Tarasovača is forgotten. This shift in name usage could be attributed to changes in local demographics and cultural influences over time. Additionally, historical events or administrative decisions might have played a role in gradually phasing out the Tarasovača name (see Puljić 2010, Naumović, Dražeta 2023).

14 e.g. Hanson, Oltean 2013.

15 NCAP 2024b.

16 NCAP 2024c.

17 NCAP 2024d.

18 NCAP 2024a.

Sl. 2. Fotografija iz zraka katuna Tarasovača i Busovača i krajolika oko njih, s identificiranim antropogenim arhitektonskim i pastoralnim elementima (autor: L. Škerjanec).

Fig. 2. Orthophoto of the Tarasovača and Busovača katuns and the landscape around them, with marked anthropogenic architectural and pastoral elements (author: L. Škerjanec).

svjetskog rata također nije bila uspješna.¹⁹ Fotografije iz sredine 20. vijeka bile bi ključne za utvrđivanje obima aktivnih naselja jer su ratne, a posebno poratne aktivnosti (oduzimanje imovine, protjerivanje) promijenile društvenu dinamiku i intenzitet korištenja zemljišta. Veliku nadu polažemo u arhiv Vojnogeografskog instituta u Beogradu.

to date.¹⁹ Photographs from the mid-20th century would be crucial to identifying the extent of active settlement, as the wartime and especially post-war activities (confiscation of property, expulsion) have changed the social dynamics and intensity of land use. We put great hope in this regard into the archive of the Vojnogeografski Institut in Belgrade.

¹⁹ HES 2024.

¹⁹ HES 2024.

Američki program Corona, prvi program satelitskog snimanja, pokrenut je 1958. Između 1960. i 1972. generirano je više od 800.000 slika koje su postale javno dostupne 1995.²⁰ Ove optičke satelitske slike visoke rezolucije, jednostavne za korištenje, fundamentalno su promijenile tumačenje fotografije krajolika.²¹ Slike programa Corona posebno su vrijedne jer prethode modernom intenziviranju poljoprivrednih aktivnosti, porastu rudarstva otvorenog kopa, industrijskom razvoju i urbanoj ekspanziji širom svijeta. Ove su slike vrlo koristan izvor informacija za područja gdje nisu dostupne historijske zračne fotografije. U arheologiji su slike rezolucije 1,8 m prvi put korištene za identifikaciju dobro vidljivih lokacija u polusušnim aluvijalnim ravninama Bliskog istoka.²² Razvijeni su sofisticirani postupci ortorektifikacije za podešavanje svjetlosnih snopova grupe fotografija.²³ Neki od tih pristupa u javnoj su upotrebi,²⁴ ali su nepotrebni za analizu relativno malih područja s ograničenim brojem slika, gdje su sasvim dovoljne i jednostavnije metode, kao što je i ovdje slučaj. Za katune Busovača i Tarasovača inicijalno smo identificirali i posmatrali devet fotografija visoke rezolucije pet datuma (9. maj 1968 – 26. maj 1972). Međutim, iako automatski izračunati otisci sugeriraju drugačije, neke od njih ne pokrivaju područje koje se proučava. Uzorak DS1111-1036AF001 snimljen je 25. jula 1970. i ima prostornu rezoluciju od 1,8 m (sl. 3a).²⁵

Drugi američki program, Hexagon (KH-9), upravljao je serijom fotografskih izviđačkih satelita između 1971. i 1984. Oznaka tajnosti je uklonjena, tj. slike su učinjene dostupnim javnosti 2011, kao nastavak iste vladine uredbe kao i za slike programa Corona. Šeststo sedamdeset hiljada slika postalo je dostupno 2020.²⁶ Rezolucija panchromatskih stereokamera dosegla je 0,6 m i uporediva je s modernim satelitima.²⁷ Fizičke dimenzije okvira su ogromne, 0,17 m x (obično) 2,4 m, a teritorija prikazana na jednom okviru je također izuzetno velika, do 24 km x 580 km. Dok su se prijašnji izviđački sateliti prvenstveno koncentrisali na Sovjetski Savez, istočnu Evropu i Kinu, Hexagonov kapacitet je bio takav da je omogućio dobivanje barem nekih slika za najveći dio planete.²⁸ To se ogleda u broju dostupnih slika za planinu Crvanj i visoravan Morine: postoji 60 slika visoke rezolucije (0,6–1,2 m) za 34 datuma, od 17. juna 1971. do 1. augusta 1984. Slike od 13 datuma su mutne, a od četiri datuma su kose. Uzorak D3C1203-300461F066 (sl. 3b) snimljen je 11. augusta 1972. i sa prostranom rezolucijom od 1,2 m.²⁹

WorldView-2 bio je prvi komercijalni multispektralni satelit visoke rezolucije, s osam spektralnih senzora.

The US Corona programme, the first imaging satellite programme, was launched in 1958. Between 1960 and 1972, it generated over 800,000 images, which were made publicly available in 1995.²⁰ This user-friendly, high-resolution optical satellite imagery has revolutionised landscape photo interpretation.²¹ The Corona imagery is particularly valuable as it predates modern agricultural intensification, as well as the growth of open-pit mining, industrial development and urban expansion across the globe. These images are a highly beneficial source of information for areas where historical aerial photographs are unavailable. In archaeology, these 1.8 m resolution images were first used to identify highly visible sites in the semi-arid alluvial plains of the Near East.²² Sophisticated orthorectification procedures have been developed for bundle block adjustment of a set of images;²³ although certain such approaches are applied globally,²⁴ they are unnecessary for the analysis of relatively small areas with a limited number of images, where more straightforward methods work just as well, as is our case. For the Busovača and Tarasovača katuns, we initially identified and accessed nine high-resolution images from five dates (ranging between 9 May 1968 and 26 May 1972). However, although the automatically calculated footprints suggest otherwise, some of these do not cover the area under study. An example image, DS1111-1036AF001, was acquired on 25 July 1970 and has a 1.8 m spatial resolution (Fig. 3a).²⁵

Another US programme, Hexagon (KH-9), involved the operation of a series of photographic reconnaissance satellites between 1971 and 1984. The imagery obtained was declassified, i.e. released for public use, in 2011, as a continuation of the same governmental decree as the Corona programme images. The 670,000 images became available in 2020.²⁶ The resolution of the stereo panchromatic cameras reached 0.6 m and is comparable to modern satellites.²⁷ The physical frame dimensions are massive – 0.17 m by (typically) 2.4 m – and the territory imaged on a single frame is vast, up to 24 x 580 km. While previous reconnaissance satellites had been primarily concentrated on the Soviet Union, Eastern Europe and China, Hexagon's capacities allowed it to acquire at least some imagery for most of the planet.²⁸ This is reflected in the number of images available for the Crvanj mountain and Morine plateau: there are 60 high-resolution (0.6-1.2 m) images from 34 dates, from 17 June 1971 to 1 August 1984. Images from 13 dates are cloudy, and from four dates are oblique. An example image, D3C1203-300461F066 (Fig. 3b), was acquired on 11 August 1972 and had a spatial resolution of 1.2 m.²⁹

20 USGS 2008.

21 Day *et al.* 1998, 38–39.

22 Ur 2013, 22; Casana, Cothren 2013, 33–35.

23 Ghuffar *et al.* 2022.

24 Casana 2020.

25 EROS Center 2017a.

26 EROS Center 2017b.

27 Burnett 1982; Oder *et al.* 1992.

28 Berkowitz 2012.

29 Snimcima programa Corona i Hexagon može se pristupiti besplatno na stranici Geološkog topografskog instituta Sjedinjenih Država (USGS), na odjelu EarthExplorer: <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>.

20 USGS 2008.

21 Day *et al.* 1998, 38–39.

22 Ur 2013, 22; Casana, Cothren 2013, 33–35.

23 Ghuffar *et al.* 2022.

24 Casana 2020.

25 EROS Center 2017a.

26 EROS Center 2017b.

27 Burnett 1982; Oder *et al.* 1992.

28 Berkowitz 2012.

29 The Corona and Hexagon images can be accessed free of charge at the US Geological Survey's (USGS) EarthExplorer website: <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>.

Sl. 3. Katuni Busovača i Tarasovača na satelitskim snimcima: a-Corona (25. jula 1970), b-Hexagon (11. augusta 1972) i c-WorldView-2 (22. oktobra 2012, ©2012 Maxar Technologies); d-jugoistočni rub planine Crvanj i jugozapadni kraj visoravni Morine na savremenoj satelitskoj snimci, s područjem istraživanja označenim bijelim kvadratom. Ostaci objekta prikazani su preuveličano crvenom bojom, a ostali zidovi narandžastim linijama (autor: Ž. Kokalj).

Fig. 3. The Busovača and Tarasovača katuns as seen on a-Corona (25 July 1970), b-Hexagon (11 August 1972), and c-WorldView-2 (22 October 2012, © 2012 Maxar Technologies) satellite images; d-the southeastern edge of Crvanj mountain and southwestern end of the Morine plateau on a modern satellite image, with the study area delineated by a white square. The building's remains are shown exaggerated in red, and other walls as orange lines (author: Ž. Kokalj).

Omogućuje izoštrene slike s rezolucijom od 0,5 m. Za razliku od satelita u programima Corona i Hexagon, manevarska sposobnost satelita WorldView-2, njegovi digitalni senzori i pomoćni sistemi omogućavaju da se slike dobiju, uz vrhunsku preciznost i mnogo većom brzinom, što osigurava efikasnost i pouzdanost. Njime upravlja kompanija Maxar, a

Launched in 2009, WorldView-2 was the first commercial high-resolution 8-band multispectral satellite. It provides pan-sharpened colour imagery with a resolution of 0.5 m. Unlike the satellites in the Corona and Hexagon programmes, WorldView-2's manoeuvrability, digital sensors and ancillary systems enable it to acquire images with pinpoint accuracy and at a much faster rate, ensuring efficiency

Sl. 4. DEM Digitalni elevacijski model katuna Tarasovača i Busovača i krajolik oko njih, s identificiranim antropogenim arhitektonskim i pastoralnim elementima (autor: L. Škerjanec).

Fig. 4. DEM of the Tarasovača and Busovača katuns and the landscape around them, with marked anthropogenic architectural and pastoral elements (author: L. Škerjanec).

nudi slike po principu *open source* u svojoj online arhivi.³⁰ Za naše područje istraživanja, ove slike visoke rezolucije u boji pomažu u identifikaciji suhih kamenih zidova koji mogu biti nevidljivi ili zaklonjeni na slici iz jednog datuma. Zidovi se najlakše prepoznaju na slikama gdje je pozadina – trava ili kamen – homogena i neometana procesima kao što je rezanje (sl. 3c).

Sveobuhvatna analiza podataka daljinskih istraživanja o promjenjivom krajoliku Crvnja i Morine treća je faza prostorne analize u okviru ovog projekta i trenutno je u toku. Završena je prva faza, prikupljanje podataka, i druga faza, digitalizacija svih vidljivih tragova ljudskog uticaja na ovaj planinski krajolik. Identificirani su, tipizirani i evidentirani zidovi građevina, pomoćni objekti, torovi i slične građevine koje je napravio čovjek na području od oko 20 km² oko Busovače i Tarasovače, kao i okolnih katuna (sl. 2, 3d). Napuštanje katuna imalo je šire ekološke posljedice. Inicijalno posmatranje i preliminarna hronološka analiza zračnih i satelitskih snimaka pokazuju da skupine bara – mreže bara koje su omogućavale stanovanje u brdima jer su osiguravale vodu za stoku, ljude i biljke – sada nestaju. Iako je u nekim

and reliability. Operated by Maxar, it offers open-source images in its online archive.³⁰ For our study area, this high-resolution colour imagery assists in identifying dry-stone walls that may be invisible or obscured in an image from a single date. Walls are most easily identified in images where the background – grass or rock – is homogeneous and undisturbed by processes such as cutting (Fig. 3c).

A comprehensive analysis of the remote sensing data about the changing landscape of Crvanj and Morine is the third phase of the spatial analysis within the project, and is currently underway. The first phase (gathering data) and the second phase (digitising all visible traces of human impact on this mountainous landscape), have both been completed. The walls of buildings, auxiliary structures, corrals and similar human-made constructions in an area of approximately 20 km² around Busovača and Tarasovača, as well as the surrounding katuns, have been identified, typified and recorded (Fig. 2, 3d). The abandonment of the katuns had broader ecological consequences. The initial observation and preliminary chronological analysis of aerial and satellite imagery indicate that the pond families – networks of ponds that enabled dwelling in the uplands by providing

slučajevima uglavnom povoljno iskorištena prirodna depresija s dotokom kišnice, u drugim je slučajevima dno bare očvrstnuto kako bi postalo nepropusno (vještački modificirano), a obale su ojačane zidom. Zbog ovih antropogenih intervencija ovakva jezercica zahtijevaju redovno održavanje. Međutim, mnoga od njih sada nemaju vode i pretvorena su u livade s bujnom vegetacijom zbog poboljšanog zadržavanja vlage u tlu. Nestanak izvora vode, skupa s propadanjem pastoralnih praksi u planinskom krajoliku, označava stalne ekološke i kulturne promjene planina.

ARHEOLOGIJA STRUKTURA

Vernakularnu arhitekturu širom svijeta proučavaju razni naučnici, uključujući arheologe, antropologe, istraživače iz oblasti društvenih nauka, semiotičare, antropogeografe, etnografe i psihologe okoliša. Prema razvijenom interaktivnom ili sociološko-ekološkom modelu, okolina i ponašanje su u međuzavisnom odnosu i utječu jedno na drugo. Naglašava se dinamička interakcija unutar antropogenog sistema

water for livestock, people and plants – are now disappearing. Although primarily favourable natural depressions with rainwater inflow were utilised in some cases, in others the pond base was hardened (i.e. artificially modified) to make it impermeable, with the banks being fortified with walls. Due to these anthropogenic interventions, such ponds require regular maintenance. However, many now lack water and have turned into meadows with lush vegetation due to improved soil moisture retention. The disappearance of water sources in parallel with the decline of pastoral practices in the mountainous landscape signifies the highlands' ongoing environmental and cultural changes.

STANDING ARCHAEOLOGY

Vernacular architecture across the globe has been studied from the perspective of various disciplines, including archaeology, anthropology, the (broader) social sciences, semiotics, human geography, ethnography, and environmental psychology. The interactive or sociological-ecological model that has been developed argues that the relationship

Sl. 5. Busovača: Struktura 3 sa dvije popločane prostorije. Pod u Prostoriji 1 s kamenim pločicama otkriven je tek uklanjanjem trave. Prema gearheološkim analizama naslaga unutar nje, arhitektonskim razlikama u odnosu na druge građevine i informacijama koje su dali lokalni sagovornici, mogla je biti korištena za prerađivanje mlijeka, pri čemu je jedna prostorija bila povezana s prerađivanjem mlijeka/sira, a druga sa njihovim skladištenjem (autor: L. Škerjanec).

Fig. 5. Busovača: Structure 3 with its two paved rooms. The stone-tiled floor of Room 1 was exposed only after removal of the grass. According to gearchaeological analyses of the deposits within, architectural comparison to other buildings, and information provided by local informants, it might have been used for milk processing, with one room associated with the processing of milk/cheese, and the other with its storage (author: L. Škerjanec).

okoline, koja uključuje promjene i prilagodbe i pokazuje njegovu primjenjivost u različitim kontekstima.³¹ Ovaj model daje teorijski okvir i nudi praktične implikacije za osmišljavanje i razumijevanje izgrađene okoline. Ljudsko ponašanje utiče na organizaciju izgrađenog okoliša, a izgrađeni okoliš utiče na ponašanje, pri čemu jedno može modificirati drugo. Unutar ovog modela, identificirano je sedam faktora koji su determinante oblika kuće, bez obzira na društveni, kulturni ili geografski identitet: klima, topografija, dostupni materijali, nivo razvijenosti tehnologije, ekonomski resursi, funkcija i kulturna konvencija.³² Da bismo razumjeli kako strukture dobivaju određeni dizajn, potrebno je istražiti proces projektovanja i identificirati ključne faktore koji utiču na odluke o dizajnu određenih struktura. Na najširem nivou, arhitektonski dizajn oblikuje dostupnost materijala i tehnologije.³³ Na oblik utiče više faktora, od kojih je funkcija samo jedan: tu je i smjer prevladavajućih vjetrova, položaj mogućih izvora vode, vremenski nepovoljni uslovi koji se ponavljaju i niz kulturnih tradicija. Okolina djelomično utiče na formu, ali dublji uticaj ima dostupnost građevnog materijala.³⁴

Krški okoliš Hercegovine sastoji se od krečnjačke podloge. Krečnjak je glavni građevinski materijal koji se koristi za izgradnju životnih prostora za ljude i životinje, izgradnju mostova, popločavanje cesta, postavljanje granica i označavanje rubova; to je živo svjedočanstvo trajne vrijednosti tradicionalnih metoda gradnje. Suhozidna gradnja neraskidivo je povezana s održivom organizacijom ruralnog prostora. Umijeće suhozidne gradnje direktno je vezano uz poznavanje stijena i prirodnih materijala te općenito uz specifičnu sredinu u kojoj se primjenjuje (smjer i intenzitet vjetrova i kiše, opasnost od erozije, odrona, poplava i sl.). Suhozidni krajolici i arhitektura su opipljivi, anonimni izraz ove tradicionalne građevinske tehnike i izvanredan primjer sposobnosti čovječanstva da se prilagodi okolišu. Oni čine intimnu vezu između materijalne i nematerijalne baštine te između ljudi i prirode.³⁵ Tehnika suhozidne gradnje na području istočnog Jadrana datira još iz prahistorije i koristi se i danas, posebno u ruralnim okvirima.³⁶ Godine 2018. znanje o suhozidu i tehnika gradnje upisani su na Uneskov popis nematerijalne kulturne baštine.³⁷

Tlo oko dva katuna ispresijecano je suhozidom (sl. 2). Neki zidovi okružuju prostor, oblikujući ovalne ili pravougaone površine različitih veličina; drugi su jednostavno linije koje predstavljaju granice, ograđene prostore ili druge vrste ograničenja za životinje i ljude. Svi stambeni objekti su malih dimenzija i smješteni na kamenitim rubovima pašnjaka ili plodnog zemljišta. Upoređujući okruženje Crvnja i Morine s različitim nalazištima u transhumantnim istraživanjima

between the environment and behaviour is interdependent and mutually influential. It stresses the dynamic interaction within an anthropogenic environmental system involving change and adaptation, demonstrating its applicability in various contexts.³¹ This model provides a theoretical framework and offers practical implications for designing and understanding the built environment. Human behaviour influences the organisation of the built environment, and the built environment influences behaviour, with each having the potential to modify the other. Within this model, seven factors have been identified as the determinants of house form, regardless of social, cultural, or geographic identity: climate, topography, available materials, level of technology, economic resources, function, and cultural convention.³² To understand how structures acquire specific designs, one must explore the design process and identify the key factors that influence the decisions behind the design of particular structures. At the broadest level, architectural designs are shaped by the availability of materials and technology.³³ The form is influenced by several factors, of which function is just one; the direction of the prevailing winds, the location of possible water sources, recurring increment weather conditions, and an assortment of cultural traditions must also be taken into account. The environment exerts a partial influence on form, although a more profound impact stems from the availability of building materials.³⁴

The karst environment of Herzegovina is comprised of the limestone bedrock. Limestone is the main construction material used to build living spaces for both humans and animals, construct bridges, pave roads, establish borders and delineate edges; it stands as a living testament to the enduring value of traditional building methods. Dry-stone constructions are inextricably linked with the sustainable organisation of rural space. The art of dry-stone masonry is directly linked to the knowledge of rocks and natural materials and, generally, to the specific environment where it is applied (direction and intensity of winds and rain, risk of erosion, landslides, floods, etc.). Dry-stone landscapes and architecture are the tangible, anonymous expression of this traditional building technique, and constitute an outstanding example of mankind's ability to adapt to the environment. They form an intimate link between tangible and intangible heritage, and between human beings and nature.³⁵ The dry-wall building technique in the eastern Adriatic region dates back to the prehistoric period and is still used today, especially in rural contexts.³⁶ In 2018, this drywall knowledge and building technique was inscribed on the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage List.³⁷

The ground around the two katuns is criss-crossed with dry-stone walls (Fig. 2). Some walls enfold space, marking out

31 Noble 2013.

32 Sanders 1990, 44.

33 McGuire, Schiffer 1983, 278.

34 Noble 2013, 15.

35 UNESCO 01393.

36 Kulušić 1999.

37 UNESCO 01393. Početni upis bio je 2018. (produžen 2024) kao multinacionalna nominacija; začudo, ne uključuje Bosnu i Hercegovinu: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393>

31 Noble 2013.

32 Sanders 1990, 44.

33 McGuire, Schiffer 1990, 278.

34 Noble 2013, 15.

35 UNESCO 01393.

36 Kulušić 1999.

37 UNESCO 01393. The initial inscription was in 2018 (extended in 2024) as a multinational nomination; surprisingly, it does not include Bosnia and Herzegovina: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/art-of-dry-stone-walling-knowledge-and-techniques-01393>

Sl. 6. Tarasovača: ostaci prahistorijske keramike pronađeni u geoarheološkoj testnoj jami (TP026) na sjeveroistočnoj padini iznad katuna Tarasovača, između dva kružna ograđena prostora (autor: L. Grahek).

Fig. 6. Tarasovača: fragments of prehistoric pottery found in a geoarchaeological test pit (TP026) on the northeastern slope above Tarasovača katun, between two circular enclosures (author: L. Grahek).

planinskih lanaca Apenina ili Pirineja, opći je zaključak da okrugli ograđeni prostori potiču iz prahistorijskog perioda, dok su pravougaone strukture srednjovjekovnog porijekla.³⁸ Iako ovaj trend nije vidljiv u Irskoj,³⁹ može se primijetiti na Mediteranu, uprkos nekim nedavno izgrađenim kružnim pastoralnim ograđenim prostorima.

Kvaliteta i tehnika gradnje zidova variraju zavisno od njihove funkcije i struktura koje tvore. Razlikujemo dvije vrste zidova: jednostrane i dvostrane. Iako se na prvi pogled može učiniti jednostavnom, izgradnja jednostranog zida zahtijeva vještinu i snalažljivost. Uglavnom su građeni većim kamenjem pri dnu, a manjim prema vrhu. Kamenje je složeno bez vezivnog štuta, ali se međusobno preklapa kako bi se spriječilo urušavanje. Dakle, takvi zidovi imaju mnogo proreza, a ne pravo lice. S druge strane, dvostrani zidovi (sl. 5) imaju s obje strane probrano kamenje za lice, a sredina je ispunjena sitnim kamenjem i šutom. Kamenje je čvrsto postavljeno i spojeno kako bi se uklonile sve praznine. Kod viših očuvanih zidova (1,0 m i više) vidimo sužavanje prema vrhu s obje strane – smanjenjem težine prema vrhu povećava se čvrstoća zida. Vrh zida – završni kamen – obrađen je većim, vodravno postavljenim kamenjem koje se proteže od jednog ruba preko sredine ili cijele širine zida.⁴⁰

Najviše truda i planiranja uloženo je u izgradnju ulaza u građevine, gdje možemo vidjeti pomno slagane slojeve ravnog kamenja. Ostali ulazi ili prolazi kroz (pašnjačke) zidove su jednostavniji, sa samo malim otvorom kroz koji prolaze ovce i koji je zatvoren jednostavnim drvenim vratima ili samo granom grmlja kako bi se spriječila ispaša stada.

oval or rectangular areas of different sizes; others are simply lines, representing boundaries, enclosures, or other forms of partition for animals and humans. All the residential buildings are of small dimensions and located on the stony edges of pastures or fertile land. When comparing the Crvanj and Morine setting with various sites in transhumant studies of the Apennines or the Pyrenees mountain ranges, a generalisation that the round enclosures date back to the prehistoric period, while rectangular structures are of medieval origin can be made.³⁸ While this trend is not evident in Ireland,³⁹ it can be observed in the Mediterranean, in spite of some circular pastoral enclosures having been more recently built.

The quality and construction technique of the walls vary based on their function and the structures they form. We can distinguish two types of walls: single- and double-face. Although from the outside it would appear a relatively simple task, building a single-face wall requires skill and resourcefulness. They are mostly built with larger stones at the bottom and smaller ones towards the top. The stones are stacked without binding debris, but are interlocked to prevent collapse; thus, such walls have many slits and no true 'face'. In contrast to this, double-face walls (Fig. 5) have selected face stones on both sides, and the middle is filled with rubble and debris. The stones are tightly fitted and interlocked to eliminate any gaps. Tapering towards the top from both sides – reducing the weight towards the top increases the strength of the wall – can be observed in higher preserved walls (1.0 m and over). The wall's top is finished using larger, horizontally placed stones (capstones) extending from one edge across the middle or the whole width of the wall.⁴⁰

The most effort and planning went into constructing the entrances to the structures, where we can see the careful layering of flat stones. Other entrances or passages through

38 Walsh et al. 2014; García-Casas, Gassiot Ballbè 2022.

39 Cf. Aalen 1964.

40 Kremenčić 2022; Čok 2014.

38 Walsh et al. 2014; García-Casas, Gassiot Ballbè 2022.

39 Cf. Aalen 1964, 15.

40 Kremenčić 2022; Čok 2014.

Od svih suhozidnih konstrukcija samo su dva jasna kružna ograđena prostora, oba smještena na padini istočno od katuna Tarasovača i označena kao torovi. Graditelji su iskoristili prirodni raspored i krečnjačke izdanke kao zidni okvir. Ovi pojedinačni zidovi sačuvani su do tri sloja kamenja. Za razliku od većine drugih zidova u katunima Busovača i Tarasovača, kamen koji je korišten za ove zidove nije bio obrađen niti posebno odabran. Čini se da su bili neselektivno položeni ili umetnuti u otvore između izdanaka stijene, a ne pažljivo složeni u slojeve, kao u stambenim zgradama ili nekim dijelovima koliba za životinje. Nejasno je ukazuje li to na specifičnu tehniku gradnje ili je posljedica protoka vremena. Međutim, njihov kružni oblik i blizina prahistorijskog kamenog tumulusa – oko 75 m jugoistočno – potaknuli su nagađanja o njihovom prahistorijskom porijeklu. I ubrzo je stigao odgovor.

Tokom geoarheološkog istraživanja, postavljena je jedna od testnih jama (TP206) između dva kružna ograđena prostora. Na dubini od 15 cm pronašli smo tri fragmenta prahistorijske keramike (sl. 6). Proučavajući tehnike ručnog oblikovanja tih fragmenata i tehnološke karakteristike materijala, pronašli smo analogije u keramici kasnog bronzanog i starijeg željeznog doba sa šireg geografskog područja, sve do gromila Hatelji u Dabarskom polju, udaljenih oko 70 km. To sugerira da je Tarasovača možda bila dio razgranate mreže u tom razdoblju, što ukazuje na moguće interakcije između (različitih) grupa i širenje tehnoloških i umjetničkih uticaja. Još nije sigurno da li je razlog umrežavanja bila trgovina ili transhumantna ekonomija. Potrebno je više istraživanja usmjerenih na prahistorijske elemente planinskih područja. Buduća istraživanja obrazaca naseljavanja i socioekonomskih struktura zajednica koje su u to vrijeme nastanjivale regiju pružit će uvid u njihov svakodnevni život, ekonomsku praksu i društvene interakcije tokom ovih transformativnih razdoblja.

GROBLJE

Nekropola je prilikom naše prve posjete ostala skrivena zbog visoke trave, a otkrivena je tek nakon detaljnog pregleda terena u septembru 2023. godine. Nalazi se na ledničkoj moreni, zapadno od katuna Busovača, na pola puta do lokve. Nakon što je trava pokošena, mogli smo identificirati 12 očitih grobnih oznaka (sl. 7a, b). Od toga su bila tri stećka, a devet je bilo drugog tipa: bili su izgrađeni od prirodno lomljenih kamenih ploča složenih u okvirne pravougaone oblike koji predstavljaju grobne pokrove. Osim toga, okomite kamene ploče postavljene su duž rubova grobova kako bi formirale okvir i dale obrub pojedinačnim grobnim parcelama. Tri stećka se pojavljuju u obliku ploče: dvije su neukrašene vodoravne ploče, a jedna je pravougaona ploča debljine 26 cm s uklesanim ukrasima poput rozeta, polumjeseca, mača i štita na gornjoj plohi (sl. 7b). Historijski konsenzus smješta stećke u period između 12. i 16. vijeka. Devet ukopa se izrazito razlikuje od stećaka po tipu biljega. Na osnovu njihovog izgleda

the (pasture) walls are simpler, with only a small gap for the sheep to pass through, closed off with a simple wooden gate, or even just a branch to prevent the herds from grazing.

Out of all the drywall structures, there are only two clear circular enclosures, both located on the slope east of Tarasovača katun and identified as corrals. The builders utilised the natural layout and limestone outcrops as a wall frame. These single walls are preserved with up to three layers of stones. Contrary to most other walls in the Busovača and Tarasovača katuns, the stones used for these walls were neither dressed nor specifically selected. It appears they were indiscriminately laid or inserted into the openings between the bedrock outcrops and not carefully stacked in layers, as is seen in residential buildings or some parts of animal huts. It is unclear if this indicates a specific building technique or is rather a consequence of the passage of time. However, their circular shape and the proximity of a prehistoric stone mound – about 75 m to the southeast – raised conjecture about their prehistoric origin. And the answer came soon after.

The geoarchaeological survey set one of the test pits (TP206) between the two circular enclosures. At a depth of 15 cm, we found three fragments of prehistoric pottery (Fig. 6). Upon examining their handmade shaping techniques and technological characteristics of the fabric, we found analogies in the Late Bronze Age and Early Iron Age pottery from a wider geographical area, all the way to the Hatelji mounds in Dabarsko polje, about 70 km away. This suggests that Tarasovača may have been a part of an extensive network during that period, indicating possible interactions between (different) groups and the spread of technological and artistic influences. Whether the reason for such networking was trade or the transhumant economy has not yet been established; more research focusing on the prehistoric elements of the highland areas is required. Future research into the settlement patterns and socio-economic structures of the communities inhabiting the region at the time will provide insights into their daily lives, economic practices and social interactions during these transformative eras.

BURIAL GROUND

The necropolis stayed hidden during our initial visit due to the high grass, and it was only discovered after a detailed survey of the area in September 2023. It is located on a glacial moraine, west of the Busovača katun, halfway to the water pond. Once the grass was cut, we were able to identify 12 apparent grave marker structures (Fig. 7a, b). Three of these were stećci tombstones, and nine were of a different type: they were constructed from naturally broken stone slabs assembled into roughly rectangular shapes to represent burial covers. In addition, vertical stone slabs were placed along the edges of graves to form a frame and provide a border to individual burial parcels. The three stećci appear in a slab form: two are undecorated horizontal slabs, and one is a 26 cm thick rectangular slab with carved decorations including rosettes, a crescent moon, a sword, and a shield on the upper surface (Fig. 7b). The historical consensus places stećci between the 12th and 16th centuries. The

Sl. 7. a-Nekropola Busovača: Različiti prikazi nekropole na glacijalnoj moreni, b-detalan prikaz ukrašenog stećka (autor: L. Škerjanec).

Fig. 7: a-The Busovača necropolis: various views of the necropolis on a glacial moraine, b-the detailed view of the decorated stećak (author: L. Škerjanec).

protumačili smo ih kao postsrednjovjekovne ukope, što je hipoteza koju budući iskopi i metoda datiranja upotrebom radiougljika mogu potvrditi. Međutim, ovdje se postavlja pitanje: ko su ljudi koji su ukopani uz katun Busovača? Iako je nejasna, ovo groblje dokazuje vezu između srednjovjekovnih stećaka i transhumantnog stočarstva.

GEOARHEOLOŠKA PROCJENA

Intenzivnim geoarheološkim istraživanjem obuhvaćene su pedosedimentarne sekvence povezane s različitim geomorfološkim oblicima reljefa i izgrađenim okolišem na katunima. To nam je omogućilo da otkrijemo bogatu

nine burials are distinctly different from the stećci in terms of marker type. Based on their appearance, we interpreted them as post-medieval burials, a hypothesis that future excavation and carbon analyses can corroborate. However, at this point, the question arises: Who are the people buried beside the Busovača katun? Although the connection is unclear, this burial ground proves a tangible link between medieval stećci and transhumant pastoralism.

GEOARCHAEOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT

An intensive geoarchaeological survey captured pedo-sedimentary sequences associated with different geomorphological landforms and built environments at the katuns. This

mikrohistoriju lokaliteta, kojoj se pristupa iz vizure geomorfologije i arheologije. Tokom istraživanja prikupili smo 53 masovna uzorka iz 21 testne jame (TP), ali je u analizu uključeno samo 46 njih (sl. 2, 8).

Lokacije testnih jama pažljivo su odabrane kako bi se procijenile varijacije u pedosedimentarnim sekvencama povezanim s različitim geomorfološkim oblicima reljefa i kulturnim karakteristikama, uključujući objekte, torove za životinje, otvorene prostore na različitim udaljenostima od izgrađenih struktura, izvora vode, mogućeg polja i nekropole (sl. 8).

Geoarheologija usvaja različite tehnike iz nauke o zemlji i tlu kako bi rekonstruirala prirodne i antropogene procese uključene u formiranje određenog sloja.⁴¹ Prvi korak istraživanja bila je serija analiza tla na 46 skupnih uzoraka⁴² kako bi se odredili:

1. pH vrijednost tla,
2. postotak organske tvari u tlu (SOM) i
3. količina fosfata u tlu.

Skupni uzorci tla osušeni su na zraku, lagano usitnjeni u mužaru i prosijani na veličinu od 2 mm.⁴³ Aktivna (pH-H₂O) kiselost tla mjerena je elektrometrijski u suspenziji tla, s omjerom tla i deionizirane vode 1 : 5 (v/v).⁴⁴ Ukupni sadržaj organskog ugljika određen je suhim izgaranjem i spektroskopskom analizom proizvedenog CO₂ pomoću instrumenta Vario Max CN Element Analyser.⁴⁵ Biljkama pristupačan fosfor izmjeren je nakon ekstrakcije amonijevim laktatom (AL).⁴⁶ Tlo na lokaciji klasificirano je prema WRB-ju⁴⁷ i nacionalnim klasifikacijskim sistemima.⁴⁸ Sve tri analize tla (pH, SOM i P₂O₅) provedene su u skladu s ISO protokolima, što je osiguravalo poznatu mjernu nesigurnost. Svaki od 46 uzoraka jednom je analiziran za vrijednosti pH, SOM i P₂O₅. Preciznost mjerenja provjerena je korištenjem internih i komercijalnih referentnih materijala.

Statističke analize provedene su putem R softvera (R Development Core Team, 2024), koji sadrži pakete *stats*, *car* i *ggplot2*. Primarni cilj je bio da se utvrdi mogu li se statistički potvrditi uočeni trendovi u razlikama između tipova prostora koji se odražavaju u distribuciji vrijednosti pH, SOM i P₂O₅ (sl. 9–11). Kako bi se poboljšala normalnost distribucije podataka i stabilizirala varijanca, koncentracije SOM i P₂O₅ su logaritamski transformirane. Normalnost podataka procijenjena je Shapiro-Wilkovim testom, dok je za procjenu homogenosti varijansi među tipovima prostora korišten Leveneov test. Zatim je provedena jednosmjerna analiza varijanse (ANOVA) kako bi se ispitala razlike među vrstama prostora. Rezultati ANOVA-e su pokazali statistički značajne razlike za pH ($p < 0,001$) i marginalno značajne

allowed us to uncover the site's rich micro-history, accessed through geomorphological and archaeological lenses. During the survey, we collected 53 bulk samples from 21 test pits (TP), however only 46 were included in the analysis (Fig. 2, 8).

The locations of the TPs were carefully chosen to assess variations in pedo-sedimentary sequences associated with different geomorphological landforms and cultural features, including buildings, animal corrals, open spaces at varying distances from built structures, water sources, a putative field, and the necropolis (Fig. 8).

Geoarchaeology adopts various techniques from earth and soil sciences to reconstruct natural and anthropogenic processes involved in the formation of a particular deposit.⁴¹ As a first step of research, a series of soil analyses were undertaken on 46 bulk samples⁴² to specify:

1. the pH of the soil;
2. the percentage of the soil organic matter (SOM); and
3. the amount of phosphate in the soil.

Bulk soil samples were air-dried, gently powdered with a mortar and pestle, and sieved to a 2 mm size.⁴³ Active (pHH₂O) soil acidity was measured electrometrically in a soil suspension, with a 1:5 (v/v) ratio of soil and deionised water.⁴⁴ The total organic carbon content was determined with dry combustion and spectroscopic analysis of the produced CO₂ using a Vario Max CN Element Analyser.⁴⁵ Plant-available phosphorus was measured after extraction with ammonium lactate (AL).⁴⁶ The soil at the site was classified according to the WRB⁴⁷ and national classification systems.⁴⁸ All three soil analyses (pH, SOM, and P₂O₅) were conducted in accordance with ISO protocols, ensuring known measurement uncertainty. Each of the 46 samples was analysed one time for its pH, SOM, and P₂O₅ values. Measurement accuracy was verified using both internal and commercial reference materials.

Statistical analyses were conducted using R software (R Development Core Team, 2024), utilising the *stats*, *car*, and *ggplot2* packages. The primary objective was to determine whether the observed trends in differences between space types, reflected in the distribution of pH, SOM, and P₂O₅ values (Fig. 9–11), could be statistically confirmed. To enhance the normality of data distribution and stabilise variance, SOM and P₂O₅ concentrations were log-transformed. Data normality was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test, while Levene's test was employed to evaluate the homogeneity of variances among space types. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was then performed to examine differences across space types. The ANOVA results indicated statistically significant differences for pH ($p < 0.001$) and marginally significant differences for P₂O₅ ($p = 0.060$), but no statistically significant differences for SOM ($p = 0.863$). To further

41 Canti, Corcoran 2015; Rapp, Hill 2018.

42 Veliki uzorci s pojilišta (TP019), mogućeg polja (TP021) i groblja (TP020) nisu uključeni u ovaj rad.

43 SIST ISO 11464: 2006.

44 SIST EN ISO 10390: 2022.

45 SIST ISO 10694: 1996.

46 ÖNORM L 1087: 2006 (modifikacija AL ekstrakcije).

47 Zech *et al.* 2021.

48 Resulović *et al.* 2008.

41 Canti, Corcoran 2015; Rapp, Hill 2018.

42 Bulk samples from a watering hole (TP019), a putative field (TP021), and a cemetery (TP020) were not included in this paper.

43 SIST ISO 11464: 2006.

44 SIST EN ISO 10390: 2022.

45 SIST ISO 10694: 1996.

46 ÖNORM L 1087, 2006 (modification AL extraction).

47 Zech *et al.* 2021.

48 Resulović *et al.* 2008.

Sl. 8. Istraživanje je uključivalo relativno ravan središnji dio lokacije (TP001 – TP006, TP012, TP013), male grebene koji se protežu u pravcu SZ–Jl preko njega (TP009 – TP011, TP014, TP015), nekoliko vrtača (duboka – TP007 i TP008, te šira i plića – TP021), vrh malog humka povezanog s prizemnom morenom (TP020) i padinama na SI rubu nalazišta (TP024 – TP026). Iz arheološke perspektive, TP-i su izvađeni iz pet objekata (TP004, TP010, TP012, TP014, TP015), pet torova (TP001 – TP003, TP007 – TP009, TP011, TP024 – TP025), četiri otvorena prostora smještena na različitim udaljenostima od izgrađene strukture (TP005 – TP006, TP013, TP026), pojilišta (TP019), mogućeg polja (TP021) i groblja (TP020) (autor: L. Škerjanec).

Fig. 8. The survey included the relatively flat central section of the site (TP001 – TP006, TP012, TP013), small ridges running NW-SE across it (TP009 – TP011, TP014, TP015), a couple of dolines (a deep one (TP007 and TP008), and a wider and shallower one (TP021)), the top of a small mound associated with the ground moraine (TP020) and the slopes at the NE edge of the site (TP024 – TP026). From an archaeological perspective, the TPs were extracted from five buildings (TP004, TP010, TP012, TP014, TP015), five corrals (TP001 – TP003, TP007 – TP009, TP011, TP024, TP025), four open spaces located at varying distances from built structures (TP005, TP006, TP013, TP026), a watering hole (TP019), a putative field (TP021), and a cemetery (TP020) (author: L. Škerjanec).

razlike za P₂O₅ (p = 0,060), ali ne i statistički značajne razlike za SOM (p = 0,863). Kako bi se dodatno istražile razlike u parovima među grupama primijenjen je Tukeyev HSD test.

Preliminarni geoarheološki rezultati pokazuju da je područje istraživanja geomorfološki dinamična sredina, u kojoj intenzitet antropogenog signala lokalno varira. Na osnovu morfoloških opisa iskopanih pedosedimentarnih sekvenci, procjene njihove teksture na terenu i pH analize (tab. 1, sl. 8, 9), na lokalitetu su identificirane tri referentne

investigate pairwise differences between groups, Tukey's HSD test was applied.

The preliminary geoarchaeological results indicate that the study area is a geomorphologically dynamic environment, in which the intensity of the anthropogenic signal varies locally. Based on the morphological descriptions of the excavated pedo-sedimentary sequences, their textural assessment in the field, and their pH analysis (Tab. 1, Fig. 8, 9), three reference soil groups with distinct geomorphological

Sp.Type / tip prostora	Test Pit (TP) istražna sonda	Soil Reference group (WRB)	Jedinica tla u nac. klasifikaciji*	Soil Horizon / horizon tla	Depth / dubina [cm]	Soil Text. Assessm. / tekst. klasa tla	pH (H ₂ O)	SOM / humus [%]	P ₂ O ₅ [mg/kg]
Buildings / zgrade	TP004	Leptosols and Phaeozems	crnica i smeđa tla na krečnjacima	Ah	0 - 5	SiL	5.8	11	69
				AB	5 - 42	SiL - CL	6.2	4.8	64
				A	0 - 9	L - SiL	5.6	10.2	60
	TP010	Eutric Cambisols	eutrična smeđa tla	AB	9 - 20	CL	6.0	4.3	32
				Brz	20 - 40+	CL - C	6.2	3.4	376
	TP012	Leptosols and Phaeozems	crnica i smeđa tla na krečnjacima	Ah	above sp**	SiL	6.6	49.3	811
				AB	below sp***	L	7.6	13.4	2221
	TP014	Eutric Cambisols	eutrična smeđa tla	A	0 - 9	L	6.3	10.2	527
				AB	9 - 20	SL - L	6.4	4.5	430
	TP015	anthropogenic sequence	antropogena tla	I	0 - 18	L	6.4	29.5	1255
II				18 - 25	CL	6.9	6.4	1502	
III				25 - 40+	CL - C	6.9	3.4	911	
Corrals / torovi	TP001	Dystric Cambisols	kisela smeđa tla	Oh	0 - 5	-	5.2	21.6	334
				A	5 - 34	L	5.2	7.6	334
				AB	34 - 42	L - SL	5.1	3.4	334
	TP002	Dystric Cambisols	kisela smeđa tla	Ah	0 - 8	L	6.2	10	334
				AB	8 - 19	SL - L	5.6	5.2	334
				B	19 - 25+	L	5.4	3.8	435
	TP003	Dystric Cambisols	kisela smeđa tla	Ah	0 - 9	L - SiL	5.5	15.7	137
				AB	9 - 20	L	5.6	7.1	101
	TP007	Leptosols and Phaeozems	crnica i smeđa tla na krečnjacima	Ah	0 - 8	SiL	5.7	16	266
				AB	8 - 22	SiL - CL	6.6	8.6	243
				A	0 - 12	L	5.6	10.9	78
	TP008	Eutric Cambisols	eutrična smeđa tla	AB	12 - 42	L - SiL	5.8	5.9	256
				Ah	0 - 9	L	5.5	12.1	215
	TP009	Dystric Cambisols	kisela smeđa tla	AB	9 - 22	L	5.2	5.2	133
				B1	22 - 60	L	5.3	4.7	46
				A	0 - 9	L - SiL	5.9	13.1	229
	TP011	Eutric Cambisols	eutrična smeđa tla	AB	9 - 25	CL	6.6	8.3	87
				B	25 - 35+	CL - C	6.6	4.3	23
	TP024	Leptosols and Phaeozems	crnica i smeđa tla na krečnjacima	Ah	0 - 6	L - SiL	5.3	13.1	128
A2				6 - 50	L - SiL	5.3	6.4	92	
TP025			Ah	0 - 6	SiL - L	5.8	12.8	293	
Open Spaces / otvoreni prostori	TP005	Dystric Cambisols	kisela smeđa tla	A	0 - 8	L - SL	5.3	13.1	110
				AB	8 - 38	L - SL	5.1	7.8	119
	TP006	Dystric Cambisols	kisela smeđa tla	A	0 - 10	L	4.9	17.6	78
				AB	10 - 36	SL - L	4.8	7.9	87
	TP013	Dystric (?) Cambisols	kisela/eutrična smeđa tla	B	36 - 48+	SiL	4.8	5.7	82
				A	0 - 9	L - SL	5.9	7.8	426
				AB	9 - 24	SL - L	6.0	4.7	284
TP026	Leptosols and Phaeozems	crnica i smeđa tla na krečnjacima	B1	24 - 47	SiL	5.7	3.8	247	
			Ah	0 - 6	L - SiL	5.9	14.1	160	
			A2	6 - 18	L - SiL	6.0	7.2	60	

* Resulović et al. 2008; ** above stone paving / iznad kamenog popločanja; ***below stone paving / ispod kamenog popločanja

Tabela 1. Karakteristike tla pojedinih horizonata unutar TP-a (A. Prijatelj i M. Zupan).

Table 1. Soil characteristics of individual horizons within the TPs (by A. Prijatelj and M. Zupan).

Space Type / tip prostora	Soil Horizon (no. of horizons analysed) / horizont tla (broj analiziranih horizonata)	Depth in cm / dubina u cm (min./max. - min./max.)	pH (H ₂ O)			Soil Organic Content / organska materija tla (humus) [%]			P ₂ O ₅ [mg/kg]		
			Mean*	Standard Deviation**	Range (Min.-Max. Value)***	Mean*	Standard Deviation**	Range (Min.-Max. Value)***	Mean*	Standard Deviation**	Range (Min.-Max. Value)***
Buildings*	A (5)	0 - 5/18	6.2	0.4	5.6 - 6.4	22.0	17.3	10.2 - 49.3	544.4	509.2	60 - 1255
	AB (5)	5/18 - 20/42	6.6	0.7	6.0 - 7.6	6.7	3.8	4.3 - 13.4	849.8	970.6	32 - 2221
	B (2)	20/25 - 40+	6.6	0.5	6.2 - 6.9	3.4	0.0	3.4 - 3.4	643.5	378.3	376 - 911
Corrals**	A (10)	0/5 - 6/34	5.6	0.3	5.2 - 6.2	11.8	3.1	6.4 - 16.0	210.6	96.9	78 - 334
	AB (7)	6/34 - 19/50	5.8	0.6	5.1 - 6.6	6.2	1.9	3.4 - 8.6	212.6	105.6	101 - 334
	B (4)	19/50 - 25/60+	5.8	0.6	5.3 - 6.6	4.2	0.4	3.8 - 4.7	135.3	200.1	23 - 435
Open Spaces***	A (5)	0 - 6/10	5.6	0.5	4.9 - 6.0	12.0	4.4	7.2 - 17.6	166.8	149.8	60 - 426
	AB (3)	6/10 - 18/38	5.3	0.6	4.8 - 6.0	6.8	1.8	4.7 - 7.9	68.0	105.7	87 - 284
	B (2)	18/38 - 47/48+	5.2	0.6	4.8 - 5.7	4.8	1.3	3.8 - 5.7	164.5	116.7	82 - 247

*srednja vrijednost; **standardna devijacija; ***minimalno-maksimalne vrijednosti

*zgrade; **torovi; ***otvoreni prostori

Tabela 2. Srednje vrijednosti, standardna devijacija i minimalne i maksimalne vrijednosti za pH, organsku tvar tla (SOM) i P₂O₅ u horizontima A, AB i B uzete iz objekata, torova i otvorenih prostora (autori: A. Prijatelj i M. Zupan).

Table 2. Mean, standard deviation & minimum–maximum values for pH, soil organic matter (SOM), & P₂O₅ in the A, AB & B horizons sampled from buildings, corrals and open spaces (by A. Prijatelj and M. Zupan).

grupe tla s različitim geomorfološkim korelacijama.⁴⁹ Dystric Cambisols⁵⁰ zabilježen je u relativno ravnom središnjem dijelu, gdje su lokalni glečeri i procesi na padinama taložili nekarbonatne naslage. Tla na ovim područjima imaju visok sadržaj krupnih kamenih fragmenata (> 2 mm) koji prema terenskoj procjeni mogu dostići i 40% ispitivanih horizonata tla. Lagane su do srednje teksture, s najčešćim teksturnim klasama koje uključuju pjeskovitu ilovaču (SL), ilovaču (L) i muljevitilovaču (SiL), a klasificiraju se kao kisele (pH ≤ 5,5; tab. 1).

Područje istraživanja je prvenstveno sastavljeno od mezozojskih stijena krečnjak bogat crtom,⁵¹ sa Dystric Cambisols naizmjenično sa eutričnim kambisolima⁵² i raznim vrstama feozema. Ove grupe tla prelaze u Leptosols⁵³ na gornjim padinama i prema vrhu centralnih grebena. U poređenju

correlations were identified at the site.⁴⁹ Dystric Cambisols⁵⁰ were recorded in the relatively flat central section, where local glaciers and slope processes deposited noncarbonate debris. The soils in these areas have a high content of coarse rock fragments (> 2 mm) that can reach up to 40% of the examined soil horizons according to the field assessment. They are light-to-medium-textured, with the most common textural classes including sandy loam (SL), loam (L) and silty loam (SiL), and classified as acidic (pH ≤ 5.5; Tab. 1).

The study area is composed of Mesozoic rocks, primarily limestone rich in chert,⁵¹ with the Dystric Cambisols alternating with Eutric Cambisols⁵² and various types of Phaeozems. These soil groups transition to Leptosols⁵³ on the upper slopes and towards the top of the central ridges. Compared to soils in the flat central section, Eutric Cambisols and Phaeozems situated at the foot of the ridges and lower parts of the

49 Resulović et al. 2008; Zech et al. 2021.

50 Resulović et al. 2008.

51 Hrvatović 2006.

52 Resulović et al. 2008.

53 Resulović et al. 2008.

49 Resulović et al. 2008; Zech et al. 2021.

50 Resulović et al. 2008.

51 Hrvatović 2006.

52 Resulović et al. 2008.

53 Resulović et al. 2008.

Tabela 3. Poređenje svojstava tla u različitim tipovima prostora; srednja vrijednost \pm standardna pogreška srednje vrijednosti. Grupe s različitim slovima označavaju statistički značajne razlike (R. Turniški).

Table 3. Comparison of soil properties across different space types; mean \pm standard error of the mean. Groups with different letters indicate statistically significant differences (by R. Turniški).

Space Type / tip prostora	pH (H ₂ O)	SOM / humus [%]	P ₂ O ₅ [mg/kg]
Buildings*	6,4 \pm 0,16 a	12,5 \pm 3,94 a	688,2 \pm 198,2 a
Corrals**	5,7 \pm 0,10 b	8,5 \pm 0,88 a	196,9 \pm 26,3 b
Open Spaces***	5,4 \pm 0,16 b	9,0 \pm 1,41 a	165,3 \pm 37,4 b

*zgrade; **torovi; ***otvoreni prostori

sa tlima u ravan središnji dio, locirani eutrični kambisoli i feozemi u podnožju grebena i nižih dijelova padina imaju manji sadržaj grubih fragmenata stijena koji može doseći do 10–20% ispitivanih horizonata tla. Takođe su teksturalno teže, varira između muljevite ilovače (SiL), ilovače (L), ilovače ilovače (CL) i gline (C), te umjereno kisele (pH \geq 6,0; Tab. 1).

Analize pH vrijednosti, organske tvari tla (SOM) i fosfata pokazale su značajne varijacije u svojstvima tla u različitim područjima, što ukazuje na složenu interakciju prirodnih i antropogenih procesa na cijeloj lokaciji. Od toga, pH analiza tla daje uvid u geogene i antropogene procese koji utiču na tlo na lokaciji, dok SOM analiza otkriva mješavinu i omjere biogenih i antropogenih tragova. S druge strane, analiza fosfata posebno pokazuje ljudsku aktivnost na lokaciji.

Varijacije pH uslova od umjereno kiselih do kiselih (tab. 1; sl. 9) odražavaju dvije zasebne vrste prisutne geologije. Prva se sastoji od karbonatnih stijena, prvenstveno krečnjaka, bogatih rožnacima, na kojima su se razvila tla umjereno kisele pH vrijednosti (\geq 6,0) te nekoliko uzoraka s granicom pH vrijednosti do neutralne ili umjereno alkalne. Druga vrsta prisutne geologije sastoji se od nekarbonatnih ostataka, taloženih lokalnim glečerima i procesima na padinama, s tlom pretežno kisele vrijednosti (\leq 5,5). Najviša srednja pH vrijednost zabilježena je na objektima, zatim u torovima i otvorenim prostorima (tab. 3). Statističkom analizom utvrđene su značajne razlike između tipova prostora ($p < 0,000$). Povećanje pH vrijednosti na objektima vjerovatno se može pripisati snažnom antropogenom uticaju, pri čemu je pepeo vjerovatno faktor koji doprinosi ovom povećanju.

Sadržaj SOM-a je složen pokazatelj koji istovremeno odražava antropogene i biogene procese na lokaciji. Područje ima planinsku klimu s relativno visokim stopama padavina u ovom području Dinarskog krša (1600–2000 mm godišnje).⁵⁴ S tlima umjereno kisele do kisele pH vrijednosti stvoreni su različiti uslovi zakopavanja na katunima Busovača i Tarasovača, što bi pogodovalo sporijoj razgradnji organske tvari. U prvom slučaju, brzina procesa razgradnje i humifikacije zavisila bi od izvora organske tvari, kao što

slopes have a smaller coarse rock fragment content that can reach up to 10–20% of the examined soil horizons. They are also texturally heavier, varying between silty loam (SiL), loam (L), clay loam (CL) and clay (C), and moderately acidic (pH \geq 6,0; Tab. 1).

The analyses of pH, soil organic matter (SOM) and phosphates evidenced a notable variation in soil properties in different areas, indicating a complex interplay of natural and anthropogenic processes across the site. Of these, the soil pH analysis provides insights into geogenic and anthropogenic processes affecting the soils, while SOM analysis reveals the mix and proportions of biogenic and anthropogenic traces. On the other hand, the phosphate analysis specifically exhibits human activity at the location.

The variations in pH conditions from moderately acidic to acidic (Tab 1; Fig. 9) reflect two discrete types of underlying geology. The first consists of the carbonate rocks, primarily limestone rich in chert, with soils developed on them having a moderately acidic pH (\geq 6,0), with a few samples having a pH edging to neutral or moderately alkaline. The second type of underlying geology comprises noncarbonate debris, deposited by local glaciers and slope processes, with soils on them being predominantly acidic (\leq 5,5). The highest mean pH value was observed in buildings, followed by corrals and open spaces (Tab. 3). Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between space types ($p < 0,000$). The increase in pH in buildings is likely attributable to strong anthropogenic influences, with ash being a probable contributing factor to this enhancement.

The SOM content acts as a complex proxy, simultaneously reflecting anthropogenic and biogenic processes at the site. The area has a mountainous climate with relatively high precipitation rates in this area of the Dinaric Karst (1600–2000 mm per year).⁵⁴ With soils having a moderately acidic to acidic pH, which created distinct burial conditions at Busovača and Tarasovača katuns, this would have favoured a slower breakdown of the organic matter. In the first instance, the rate of the decomposition and humification processes would have been dependent on the source of the organic matter, such as plant residues (i.e. primary resources) and animal and microbial products (i.e. secondary resources). The source of the

Sl. 9. Poređenje pH vrijednosti objekata, torova i otvorenih prostora, kao i vrijednosti unutar njihovih povezanih horizonata tla, pokazuje da je srednja vrijednost za horizonte A, AB i B unutar objekata bila 1,1 do 1,3 puta veća nego za iste horizonte u torovima i otvorenim prostorima. Standardna devijacija za horizonte A, AB i B (vidi tab. 2) kretala se od 0,3 do 0,7 na različitim područjima nalazišta i povećavala se s dubinom. Među tri vrste pastoralnih prostora vrijednost je najviša u objektima. Krugovi, trokuti i kvadrati predstavljaju pojedinačne mjere, crne tačke srednje vrijednosti, a križići standardnu devijaciju (A. Prijatelj i R. Turniški).

Fig. 9. Comparison of pH between buildings, corrals and open spaces and within their associated soil horizons indicates that the mean for A, AB & B horizons within buildings was 1.1 to 1.3 times higher than for the same horizons in corrals and open spaces. The standard deviation for A, AB & B horizons (see Tab. 2) ranged from 0.3 to 0.7 across different areas of the site and increased with depth. Among the three types of pastoral spaces, it was highest in buildings. Circles, triangles and squares represent individual measurements, black dots mean values, and error bars standard deviation (by A. Prijatelj and R. Turniški).

su biljni ostaci (tj. primarni resursi) i životinjski i mikrobnj proizvodi (tj. sekundarni resursi). Izvor organske tvari bio bi u velikoj mjeri podložan ljudskim aktivnostima na cijeloj lokaciji, uključujući ekstenzivnu, dugotrajnu ispašu, držanje stoke u torovima, vrtlarstvo i druge različite aktivnosti unutar objekata. Različite aktivnosti mogle bi uticati na količinu i vrstu organske tvari prisutne u različitim područjima lokacije. Stopa i stepen humifikacije bili bi dodatno određeni skupom složenih abiotičkih i biotičkih faktora, uključujući temperaturu, vlagu, pH vrijednost, geologiju osnovne stijene i vrste prisutnih mikroorganizama.⁵⁵

Sadržaj SOM-a bio je najveći u objektima, ali se nije značajno razlikovao od torova i otvorenih prostora (tab. 3). Neke su strukture mogle biti povezane s preradom hrane i mlijeka ili možda s privremenim smještajem stoke (tab. 1; sl. 10). Dok se čini da je obogaćivanje organske tvari tla u torovima i otvorenim prostorima u istom rasponu, izvor SOM-a u ove dvije vrste pastoralnih prostora bio bi izrazito različit. Unutar torova, namijenjenih za držanje stoke, primarni izvor SOM-a bio bi životinjski izmet, dok bi na

organic matter would have been to a large degree subject to human activities across the site, including the extensive long-term grazing, corralling and gardening, as well as various distinct activities within buildings. Different activities would have affected the quantity and type of organic matter present in different areas of the site. The rate and degree of humification would have been further determined by a range of complex abiotic and biotic factors, including temperature, moisture, pH, bedrock geology, and types of microorganisms present.⁵⁵

The SOM content was highest in buildings, but did not differ significantly from that of corrals and open spaces (Tab. 3). Some of the structures may have been associated with food and dairy processing, or perhaps the temporary housing of livestock (Tab. 1; Fig. 10). While the enrichment of soil organic matter within corrals and open spaces appears to be in the same range, the source of the SOM in these two types of pastoral spaces would have been markedly different. Within corrals, intended for confining livestock, the primary source of SOM would have been animal excrement, while in open

55 Cf. Apsite et al. 2000; Blume et al. 2016.

55 Cf. Apsite et al. 2000; Blume et al. 2016.

Sl. 10. Poređenje sadržaja organske tvari u tlu između objekata, torova i otvorenih prostora, kao i vrijednosti unutar njihovih povezanih horizonata tla, pokazuje da je srednja vrijednost za A horizonte unutar zgrada bila 1,8–1,9 puta veća nego u torovima i otvorenim prostorima (22,0, 11,8 i 12,0%). A horizonti unutar zgrada također imaju najveću standardnu devijaciju (tab. 2) u poređenju s torovima i otvorenim prostorima. Krugovi, trokuti i kvadrati predstavljaju pojedinačne mjere, crne tačke srednje vrijednosti, a križići standardnu devijaciju (A. Prijatelj i R. Turniški).

Fig. 10. Comparison of soil organic matter content between buildings, corrals and open spaces and within their associated soil horizons shows that the mean for A horizons within buildings was 1.8-1.9 times higher than in corrals and open spaces. The A horizons within buildings also had the highest standard deviation (Tab. 2) compared to corrals and open spaces. Circles, triangles and squares represent individual measurements, black dots mean values, and error bars standard deviation (by A. Prijatelj and R. Turniški).

otvorenim prostorima to bila biljna biomasa, koja bi se povećala nakon što bi se napustila dugotrajna, ekstenzivna ispaša.⁵⁶

Kao jedan od najvažnijih pokazatelja ljudskog stanovanja i antropogene izmjene tla,⁵⁷ obogaćivanje fosforom na lokaciji služi kao antropogeni marker, koji ukazuje na razgradnju biljnih i životinjskih ostataka i izlučevina. Kao i kod sadržaja organske tvari, najveće srednje vrijednosti fosfora zabilježene su unutar objekata (tab. 1, sl. 11). Pritom su nivoi fosfora značajno premašivali one u torovima i otvorenim prostorima koji se međusobno nisu značajno razlikovali (tab. 3). Varijabilnost unutar grupe izgrađenih objekata također je bila najveća među svim tipovima prostora (sl. 11), što je rezultiralo marginalno statistički značajnim ($p = 0,06$) razlikama između tri analizirane grupe. Očekuje se da će statističke razlike postati izraženije s većim uzorkom. Naime, i najviši i najniži nivoi fosfora zabilježeni su unutar objekata, što bi moglo sugerirati razlike u njihovoj funkciji. Značajna koncentracija organskog i anorganskog otpada unutar izgrađenih objekata mogla bi biti povezana

spaces it would have been plant biomass, increasing once the long-term, extensive grazing had been abandoned.⁵⁶

As one of the most important proxies for human habitation and anthropogenic amendment of soils,⁵⁷ phosphorus enrichment at the site serves as an anthropogenic marker, indicating the decomposition of plant and animal remains and excreta. Similar to the organic matter content, the highest mean phosphorus values were recorded within the buildings (Tab. 1, Fig. 11). Therein, phosphorus levels significantly exceeded those in corrals and open spaces, which were not significantly different from each other (Tab. 3). The variability within the building group was also the highest among all space types (Fig. 11), which resulted in marginally statistically significant ($p = 0.06$) differences between the three analysed groups. It is expected that statistical differences would become more pronounced with a larger sample size. Notably, both the highest and lowest phosphorus levels were recorded within buildings, which may be suggestive of differences in their functionality. A significant concentration of organic and inorganic waste within built structures might have been associated with food and dairy processing, or perhaps the

56 Npr. Lai, Kumar 2020; Zhang et al. 2017.

57 Npr. Bintliff, Degryse 2022; Holliday, Gartner 2007; Kolb 2017.

56 e.g. Lai, Kumar 2020; Zhang et al. 2017.

57 e.g. Bintliff, Degryse 2020; Holliday, Gartner 2007; Kolb 2017.

Sl. 11. Poređenje sadržaja fosfata između objekata, torova i otvorenih prostora te unutar njihovih povezanih horizonata tla: srednji sadržaj dostupnog fosfora bio je značajno povišen unutar sva tri tipa pastoralnog prostora i unutar sva tri ispitivana horizonta tla. Sadržaj fosfata je 2,6 do 4,75 puta veći u stambenim objektima nego u torovima, a 3,3 do 12,5 puta veći nego u otvorenim prostorima. Značajno je da su AB horizonti unutar zgrada imali najveće standardno odstupanje (vidi tab. 2), dok je standardno odstupanje za B horizonte sva tri tipa pastoralnog prostora ostalo prilično veliko. Krugovi, trokuti i kvadrati predstavljaju pojedinačne mjere, crne tačke srednje vrijednosti, a križići standardnu devijaciju (A. Prijatelj i R. Turniški).

Fig. 11. Comparison of phosphate content between buildings, corrals and open spaces and within their associated soil horizons: the mean content of the available phosphorus was significantly elevated within all three types of pastoral space and within all three soil horizons examined. The phosphate content is 2.6 to 4.75 times higher in residential buildings than corrals, and 3.3 to 12.5 times higher than in open spaces. Notably, AB horizons within buildings had the highest standard deviation (see Tab. 2), with the standard deviation for B horizons of all three types of pastoral space remaining rather large. Circles, triangles and squares represent individual measurements, black dots mean values, and error bars standard deviation (by A. Prijatelj and R. Turniški).

s preradom hrane i mliječnih proizvoda ili možda s privremenim smještajem stoke.⁵⁸ Potencijalna namjena ovih objekata uključuje skloništa za pastire, stražarnice, prostore za preradu mliječnih proizvoda, skladišta i privremene staje za mlade ili ranjene životinje.⁵⁹ To dodatno potvrđuju razlike u veličini i obliku pojedinih građevina i torova širom lokaliteta, kao i različite tehnike njihove suhozidne gradnje. Razlika u nivoima fosfata između torova i otvorenih prostora ukazuje na najmanji intenzitet antropogenog signala unutar otvorenih prostora na lokaciji.

ZAKLJUČAK

Kao praksa predaka, transhumanca je duboko ukorijenjena u znanju o okolišu i obuhvaća društvene prakse i rituale povezane s brigom o životinjama, uzgojem i upravljanjem prirodnim resursima. Sveobuhvatan društveno-ekonomski sistem razvio se oko transhumance, od regionalno specifičnih

temporary housing of livestock.⁵⁸ Potential uses for these buildings include shelters for shepherds, watchtowers, spaces for dairy product processing, storage facilities, and temporary stables for young or injured animals.⁵⁹ This is further corroborated by the differences in size and shape of the individual buildings and corrals across the site, as well as different techniques employed in their dry-stone construction. The difference in the phosphate levels between the corrals and open spaces suggests the lowest intensity of the anthropogenic signal within the open spaces at the site.

CONCLUSION

As an ancestral practice, transhumance is deeply rooted in environmental knowledge, and encompasses social practices and rituals related to animal care, breeding, and managing natural resources. A comprehensive socio-economic system has evolved around transhumance, from regional-specific types of dairy products to local handicrafts

⁵⁸ Naumović, Dražeta 2023; Puljić 2010.

⁵⁹ Naumović, Dražeta 2023; Puljić 2010.

⁵⁸ Naumović, Dražeta 2023; Puljić 2010.

⁵⁹ Naumović, Dražeta 2023; Puljić 2010.

vrsta mliječnih proizvoda do lokalnih rukotvorina i sezonskih svečanosti. Danas ova praksa nije samo lokalna tradicija već globalno prepoznat i značajan element nematerijalne baštine.⁶⁰

Složeni obrazac strategija transhumance, posmatran u historijskim i etnografskim zapisima, rezultat je kontinuiranog procesa interakcije između ljudi i krajolika i dinamičnog odgovora na društvene, političke, ekonomske i ekološke ritmove. Stoga se etnografski dokumentirane prakse transhumance na Dinaridima ne bi trebale posmatrati kao ostaci fosilnih strategija iz duboke prošlosti, već kao dinamičan odgovor na promjenjive uslove i prakse, uvijek u procesu pregovora.⁶¹ Zapravo, kao arheolozi, krajolike bismo trebali promatrati kao artefakte, kao kumulativne rezultate dugotrajne dinamičke interakcije između okoliša i ljudskih kulturnih praksi.⁶²

Katuni Busovača i Tarasovača iznad Nevesinja topografski su snimljeni u septembru 2023. i 2024. godine. Dok ćemo arhitekturu izgrađenih struktura ispitati u sljedećoj fazi istraživanja, čini se da su oba katuna bila pastoralna mjesta koja su se koristila tokom nekoliko perioda. Rezultati istraživanja sugeriraju da ova dva katuna sadrže dobro očuvane zapise prahistorijskih, srednjovjekovnih i postsrednjovjekovnih praksi transhumance. Na dva najpristupačnija ulaza u dolinu otkrivene su dvije velike antropogene kamene gomile s prahistorijskom keramikom koja upućuje na njihov prahistorijski grobni karakter. Naše početno istraživanje iz zraka otkrilo je suhozidne ograde i ostatke malih jednosobnih ili dvosobnih objekata. Pokraj staze koja prolazi tom lokacijom otkriveno je i kasnosrednjovjekovno do ranonovovjekovno groblje s najmanje 12 grobova. Osim toga, lokalni etnografski izvještaji potvrđuju nastavak korištenja područja tokom modernog doba.⁶³

Preliminarni geohemijski podaci s nalazišta pokazuju potencijal gearheološkog istraživanja za razumijevanje različitog intenziteta antropogenog signala unutar pastoralnih naselja. Signal, najjači unutar objekata, a najslabiji na otvorenim prostorima, ima važne implikacije za proučavanje pastoralnih krajolika u kojima nije sačuvana izgrađena arhitektura. Ovo naglašava potencijal gearheoloških istraživanja u takvim kontekstima, posebno važnost takvih istraživanja za razumijevanje pastoralnih krajolika.

U sljedećoj fazi istraživanja, višeskalarni i višemetodski pristup omogućit će nam identifikiranje etnografskih prikaza, posebno u kombinaciji sa snimkama iz zraka Vojnogeoografskog instituta u Beogradu, iz sredine 20. stoljeća. Daljnja gearheološka istraživanja bavit će se funkcionalnošću pojedinih građevina, torova i otvorenih prostora. Kako bismo

and seasonal festivities. Today, this practice is not just a local tradition but a globally recognised and significant element of intangible heritage.⁶⁰

The complex pattern of transhumance strategies, observed in a historical and ethnographical record, is a result of an ongoing process of interaction between people and landscape and a dynamic response to social, political, economic and environmental rhythms. Thus, ethnographically documented transhumant practices in the Dinarides should not be seen as 'fossil' strategies, remnants from the deep past, but as a dynamic response to changing conditions and practices in a constant process of (re-)negotiation.⁶¹ In fact, as archaeologists, we should look at landscapes as artefacts, as cumulative results of long-term dynamic interaction between the environment and human cultural practices.⁶²

The Busovača and Tarasovača katuns above Nevesinje were topographically surveyed in the Septembers of 2023 and 2024. While the standing archaeology will be examined in greater detail in the next phase of our research, it appears that both katuns were multi-period pastoral sites. The survey results suggest these two katuns contain a well-preserved record of prehistoric, medieval and post-medieval transhumant practices. Two large anthropogenic stone barrows were discovered at two of the most accessible entrances to the valley, with the presence of prehistoric pottery suggesting their age and use for burials. Our initial aerial survey revealed the remains of dry-stone enclosures and small one-to-two-room buildings. Next to a path traversing the site, a Late Medieval to Early Modern cemetery containing at least 12 graves was also discovered. In addition, local ethnographic reports attest to the continued use of the area throughout modern times.⁶³

The preliminary geochemical data from the site demonstrates the potential of a geoarchaeological survey to gaining an understanding of the varying intensity of the anthropogenic signal within pastoral settlements. The signal, strongest within the buildings and weakest in the open spaces, has important implications for studying pastoral landscapes where no built architecture has been preserved. This underscores the potential of the geoarchaeological survey in such contexts, highlighting its importance in understanding pastoral landscapes.

In the following research phase, the multi-scalar and multi-method approach will allow us to identify the ethnographic accounts, especially when corroborated with mid-20th century aero-photo imagery from the Vojnogeoografski Institut in Belgrade. Further geoarchaeological research will address the functionality of individual buildings, corrals and open spaces. To provide a detailed and expanded geochemical mapping and micro-contextual characterisation

60 *Transhumanca, sezonsko istjerivanje stoke*, 2023. godine opisano je na Uneskov Reprezentativni popis nematerijalne kulturne baštine čovječanstva kao multinacionalna nominacija (UNESCO 01964), ali ne uključuje Bosnu i Hercegovinu: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-01964>

61 Mlekuž 2003, 141.

62 Mlekuž Vrhovnik, Fabec 2024, 82.

63 Naumović, Dražeta 2023; Puljić 2010.

60 *Transhumance, the seasonal droving of livestock* has been in 2023 inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity as a multinational nomination (UNESCO 01964); however, it does not include Bosnia and Herzegovina: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/transhumance-the-seasonal-droving-of-livestock-01964>

61 Mlekuž 2003, 141.

62 Mlekuž Vrhovnik, Fabec 2024, 82.

63 Naumović, Dražeta 2023; Puljić 2010.

osigurati detaljno i prošireno geohemijsko mapiranje i mikrokontekstualnu karakterizaciju ovog prostora, planiramo kombinirati sistemsko bušenje većih presječnih površina s probnim iskopavanjem pojedinačnih izgrađenih struktura. Prošireni skup podataka ispitat će razloge jasnog obogaćivanja horizonata podzemnog sloja tla SOM-om i fosforom i dati odgovor na to je li to dvoje rezultat njihovih vertikalnih translokacija nakon taloženja ili pastoralnih aktivnosti tokom niza perioda na lokaciji. Također se očekuje da će statističke razlike između različitih tipova prostora postati očitije s većim uzorkom.

Geoarheološki podaci bit će integrirani s radiougljičnim datiranjem odabranih konteksta, prostornom i hronološkom analizom arheoloških obilježja, analizom postojeće arhitekture te relevantnim historijskim i etnografskim izvorima. Integracija prikazanih podataka olakšat će procjenu obima i intenziteta antropogenih promjena u Busovači i Tarasovači tokom različitih faza njihovog korištenja. U konačnici, ovo će podržati naše napore da uspostavimo i razvijemo fino kalibriran istraživački protokol za proučavanje višerazdobnih pastoralnih krajolika na zapadnom Balkanu i šire.

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of these spaces, we plan to combine systematic augering of larger transect surfaces with trial trenching of individual built structures. The expanded dataset will examine the reasons behind the distinct SOM and phosphorus enrichment of the subsoil horizons, and answer the question of whether the two result from their post-depositional vertical translocations or the multi-period pastoral activities at the site. It is also expected that statistical differences between different types of space will become more evident with a larger sample size.

The geoarchaeological data will be integrated with the radiocarbon dating of selected contexts, spatial and chronological analyses of archaeological features, analysis of standing architecture, and a synthesis of relevant historical and ethnographic sources. The integration of presented data will facilitate the assessment of the extent and intensity of anthropogenic modification at Busovača and Tarasovača during their different occupational phases. Ultimately, this will support our effort to establish and develop a finely calibrated research protocol for studying the multi-period pastoral landscapes in the Western Balkans and beyond.

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